

Rice-based cropping system in Lower Bhavani Project area in Tamil Nadu, India

K. V. Selvaraj, R. Kulandaivelu, B. Rajkannan, and P. Muthuvel, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Agricultural Research Station, Bhavanisagar 638451 India

In the Lower Bhavani Project command area, water is released in alternate years to a rice crop and a peanut crop. When there is no water, farmers who have a groundwater resource go in for sugarcane, turmeric, cotton, and other crops.

We studied four cropping sequences in a red sandy loam soil during 1984-85. A rice-based sequence with sesamum, pearl millet, turmeric, and cotton gave the highest net profit (\$2,998) with a cost-to-benefit ratio of 1.15 (see table).

This sequence could increase productivity in the region by 174%. It would reduce water use for the 2-yr period from 482 to 411 cm. □

Two-year rice-based cropping system yield, water consumption, and net return. Bhavanisagar, India, 1984-85.

Crop sequence and yield (t/ha)	Net return (US\$)	Cost:benefit ratio	Water consumption (cm)
1. Rice (3.6) peanut (1.52) sesamum (0.07) Rice (3.4) peanut (1.59) sesamum (0.58)	1095	0.54	482
2. Rice (3.6) sugarcane (105.9) sesamum (0.58) peanut (1.52)	1192	0.60	409
3. Rice (3.4) sesamum (0.71) pearl millet (2.78) turmeric (16.76) peanut (1.56)	2393	1.07	404
4. Rice (3.6) sesamum (0.72) pearl millet (2.86) turmeric (15.76) cotton (2.15)	2998	1.15	411

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Performance of rice after potato, mustard, and fallow in Bangladesh

P. K. Biswas, M. Akhteruzzaman, and A. Quasem, Regional Agricultural Research Station, Hathazari, Chittagong, Bangladesh

We conducted a 2-yr field trial Nov-Jun 1985-86 and 1986-87 to study the performance of rice after potato, mustard, and fallow with 0, 2, and 4 plowings per farmers' practice. Nine treatments were tested in a split-plot design with three replications.

Soil belonged to Sylok series, silty clay loam texture. Potato and mustard were sown in Nov for both years. Potato received 102-100-100 and mustard 80-60-40 kg NPK/ha. After harvest, the land was tilled using a bullock. Rice, 45-d-old BR3 (Biplab) seedlings, was transplanted at 25- × 15-cm spacing with 80-60-40 kg NPK/ha. NPK was applied as urea, triple superphosphate,

Table 1. Yield and yield attributes of rice following potato, mustard, and fallow.^a Bangladesh, 1985-87.

Previous crop	Yield (t/ha)		Effective tillers (no./m ²)		Field grains/panicle		1000 grain wt (g)	
	1985-86	1986-87	1985-86	1986-87	1985-86	1986-87	1985-86	1986-87
Potato	4.7 a	4.4 a	302	293	74	62 a	27.81	27.09
Mustard	3.3 b	3.4 b	275	265	66	52 b	27.21	26.93
Fallow	3.3 b	3.4 b	257	258	67	58 ab	26.17	26.98

^aMean of 3 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by LSD.

Table 2. Yield and yield attributes of rice with different numbers of plowings.^a Bangladesh, 1985-87.

Plowings (no.)	Yield (t/ha)		Effective tillers (no./m ²)		Field grains/panicle		1000 grain wt (g)	
	1985-86	1986-87	1985-86	1986-87	1985-86	1986-87	1985-86	1986-87
Zero	3.2 b	3.2 b	272	257	67	50 b	26.41	26.89
Two	3.8 ab	3.7 ab	280	276	71	60 a	26.82	26.90
Four	4.4 a	4.3 a	284	283	70	63 a	27.82	27.21

^aMean of 3 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by LSD.

and muriate of potash.

Highest yield of rice was after potato (Table 1). Rice after mustard and in

fallow gave identical yields.

Rice yield increased with number of plowings (Table 2). □